
"Research Focus" international scientific journal LLC "Ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar akademiyasi" TIN
309782477 MFO 01054 A/n: 20208000105557531001
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INFORMATION

about the acceptance of the article

20.12.2023 № 000485

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Research Focus International Scientific Journal informs you that your article,
**“ПАРАЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МАШГУЛОТ
ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ ЮҚОРИ
НАТИЖАЛАРГА ЭРИШИШ”** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10427803>) has
been accepted for publication.

The publication date of the journal is December, 2023.

Director of the “Ilm-fan va
innovatsiyalar akademiyasi”:

S.Q.Saloydinov